
***Alternaria* Toxins in Processed Tomato Products**

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ABSTRACT

Several publications report the ubiquitous presence of *Alternaria* mycotoxins in numerous fruits and vegetables. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) conducted a risk assessment on several of the key *Alternaria* toxins in 2011, including alternariol (**AOH**), alternariol monomethyl ether (**AME**), tentoxin (**TEN**), and tenuazonic acid (**TeA**). Recently, the RASFF Portal reported multiple **TeA** and **AOH** incidences in processed tomato products. Previous investigations revealed the presence of *Alternaria* mycotoxins in several tomato products. In a 2016 EFSA assessment, tomatoes and tomato-based products were identified as important contributors to dietary exposure to various *Alternaria* toxins. These products are popular in Mediterranean diets, and *Alternaria* toxin incidence data will be beneficial for future risk assessments to identify possible consumer health problems. Furthermore, *Alternaria*, which affects tomato plants, is one of the most frequent diseases impacting this crop globally. Prevention and control of the disease are fundamental. Controlling the disease requires developing measures that are effective against the pathogen and safe for the environment. In any case, fungicides used must be authorized and registered for use, application and treatment. The fundamental issue in modern tomato production is a relatively limited selection of available treatments for controlling phytopathogenic fungi, as well as the development of fungal resistance to the agents now in use.

Keywords: Mycotoxins, *Alternaria* diseases, processed tomato products, alternariol, tenuazonic acid.

INTRODUCTION

Mycotoxins are harmful substances that are naturally generated by fungi, and enter the food chain as a result of crop infection before or after harvest, and are commonly detected in cereals, dried fruits, nuts, spices, and fruiting vegetables. Mycotoxins in food and feed can induce gastrointestinal and renal problems, as well as immunological weakness and cancer in people and animals. Mycotoxins can be ingested or ingested by animals fed contaminated feed.

Temperature, rainfall, relative humidity, and plant stress all have a substantial impact on fungi's ability to create mycotoxins. Mycotoxins are thus one of the most serious food safety risks, which are exacerbated by global climate change, that may enable the development and spread of new toxins, dubbed "emerging mycotoxins" (1,2).

Alternaria toxins are secondary metabolites produced by *Alternaria* fungus species. *Alternaria* species are widely distributed in the soil as normal components of its microflora and are both saprophytes and plant pathogens, producing more than 70 toxins (3). They exhibit broad structure divergence and are commonly divided into five different classes. Some toxins such as alternariol (**AOH**), alternariol monomethyl ether (**AME**), tenuazonic acid (**TeA**), and altertoxins (**ATX**) were described to induce harmful effects in animals, including fetotoxic and teratogenic effects (4). **AOH** and **AME** were found mutagenic and clastogenic in various in vitro systems (5).

These findings prompted the European Food Safety Agency (EFSA) to publish in 2011 the first risk assessment on *Alternaria* toxins (**TeA**, **AME**, **AOH**, Tentoxin (**TEN**), and Altenuene (**ALT**)) in feed and food (6). A dietary exposure assessment to *Alternaria* toxins in the European population

was then published 5 years later (7), following a call for data, where food manufacturers, national food authorities, research institutions, academia, food business operators, and other stakeholders were invited to submit analytical data on *Alternaria* toxins in food (8).

Tenuazonic acid (**TeA**), alternariol (**AOH**), alternariol monomethyl ether (**AME**) and altertoxin I (**ATX-I**) were considered the main *Alternaria* mycotoxins because of their known toxicity and their frequent presence as natural contaminants in food.

The highest exposure to **TEN** was estimated in infants and young children, with the mean exposure between 1.6 and 33.4 µg/kg bw per day (LB–UB), and the 95th percentile exposure around 55 µg/kg bw per day (UB) in different age classes. ‘Fruiting vegetables’ (such as tomatoes) were the major contributor to the dietary exposure to **TEN**. Although based on limited data, vegetarians seem to have higher dietary exposure to *Alternaria* toxins than the general population (7).

In addition to mycotoxins generated by the fungus, so-called modified *Alternaria* toxins should be recognized. When a fungus infects a plant and creates toxins, the plant attempts to protect itself by modifying the toxins and storing them in vacuoles. In most situations, these changes are catalyzed by glucosyltransferases, resulting in glucosides of the respective analytes, or by sulphotransferases, resulting in sulphate conjugates. Both metabolite categories have previously been reported for *Alternaria* toxins. These biotransformation pathways remove the toxin from plant metabolism, but they may still pose a health risk when consumed by people or animals (9).

No regulation applies for *Alternaria* toxins in foodstuffs yet, but maximum levels are currently under consideration by the European Commission. In June 2019, a draft EU Commission Recommendation on the monitoring of three *Alternaria* toxins (**AOH**, **AME**, **TeA**) in food was issued which included benchmark values above which investigations by Food Business Operators would be appropriate to identify the factors resulting in high levels in certain foods, including processed tomato products (10). The Commission recommendation 2022/553 of 5 April 2022 on monitoring the presence of *alternaria* toxins in food, established that it is appropriate to recommend the monitoring of *Alternaria* toxins in food and the identification of the factors resulting in their high levels in certain food, and that Member States,

in close cooperation with the food business operators should monitor the *Alternaria* toxins alternariol (**AOH**), alternariol monomethyl ether (**AME**) and tenuazonic acid (**TeA**) in food, in particular in processed tomato products. If possible, other *Alternaria* toxins should also be analyzed and the results reported to the European Food Safety Authority (11).

Hence, some *Alternaria* toxins have been identified to be of relevance and recommended for monitoring.

Alternaria toxins of possible toxicological relevance which should be analyzed are:

- Alternariol (**AOH**)
- Alternariol monomethyl ether (**AME**)

Alternaria toxins of which the occurrence in feed and/or food is of relevance, and for which the analysis is appropriate, are:

- Tenuazonic acid (**TeA**)
- Tentoxin (**TEN**)
- Altenuene (**ALT**)

Other *Alternaria* toxins (such as Altertoxins (**ATX**) and *Alternaria alternata lycopersici* toxins (**AAL** toxin)) can also be analyzed but, based on the currently available information, are of less relevance.

TABLE 1 presents the Indicative level for alternariol, alternariol monomethyl ether and tenuazonic acid in processed tomato products, based on the available data in the EFSA database, above which investigations should be performed, on the factors leading to the presence of *Alternaria* toxins or on the effect of food processing. The indicative levels are not food safety levels (11). This recommendation follows a trend in Europe’s Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF), where since November 2021 at least four notifications were issued for *Alternaria* toxins (TABLE 2 below), in some cases using the indicative levels in TABLE 1 —first proposed in the Commission Draft in 2019 (10) and adopted in 2022 by the Commission recommendation 2022/553 (11)— as “Maximum Residue Levels”. It is assumed that the amounts of residues found in food must be safe for consumers and must be as low as possible (12), but this is not yet the case: those are indicative levels, above which investigations should be performed, on the factors leading to the presence of *Alternaria* toxins or on the effect of food processing (11).

TABLE 1— Indicative levels for **AOH**, **AME** and **TeA** in processed tomato products*

	Alternariol (AOH) (µg/kg)	Alternariol monomethyl ether (AME) (µg/kg)	Tenuazonic acid (TeA) (µg/kg)
Processed tomato products	10	5	500

* from the Commission recommendation 2022/553 of 5 April 2022 on monitoring the presence of *Alternaria* toxins in food

TABLE 2— RASFF notifications involving tomato products (one-year review)

Date	Notification Ref.	Subject	Country
04-04-2022	2022.1971	Chlorothalonil in panicle tomatoes from Turkey	Germany
23-03-2022	2022.171	Iprodione in fresh tomatoes from Tunisia	Italy
15-03-2022	2022.1496	Alternaria toxins in tomato paste from Italy	Germany
04-03-2022	2022.131	Chlorpyrifos-methyl in semi-dried cherry tomatoes	Belgium
03-03-2022	2022.1261	Fonicamid in tomatoes from Turkey	Netherlands
14-02-2022	2022.0846	Alternariol and tenuazonic acid in tomato preparation from Turkey via Germany	Switzerland
09-02-2022	2022.0771	Alternariol and tenuazonic acid in tomato preparation	Switzerland
27-01-2022	2022.0545	Chlorpyrifos on tomatoes from Turkey	Netherlands
27-01-2022	2022.0517	Powdery mildew on the flavouring ingredient dill and foreign body (insect) in pickled tomatoes from Poland	Germany
25-01-2022	2022.0461	Unauthorised substance chlorpyrifos metil and chlorthalonil in tomato from Turkey	Romania
18-01-2022	2022.0314	Ethylene oxide above the limits in an ingredient used in tomato meatballs from France	Italy
24-11-2021	2021.6352	Alternariol and tenuazonic acid in strained tomatoes from Italy	Germany
19-11-2021	2021.6282	Unauthorised substance chlorpyrifos in tomatoes from Albania	Romania
19-08-2021	2021.445	Salmonella spp. in tomato flakes from China, processed in Germany	Germany
29-07-2021	2021.4032	Ethylene oxide in Tomato and Toscan sauce from Denmark	Netherlands
21-04-2021	2021.1986	Glass fragments in fish product (herring in tomato sauce) from the Czech Republic	Austria
12-04-2021	2021.1795	Oxamyl in tomatoes from Albania	Croatia
07-04-2021	2021.1737	Possible foreign body (glass) in dried tomatoes from Greece	Germany

ALTERNARIA DISEASES IN TOMATO

Tomato is susceptible to a variety of plant illnesses caused by fungi, bacteria, phytoplasma, virus and viroid pathogens, due to its genetic characteristics. In the Mediterranean basin the most common fungi in tomato are *Alternaria solani* (*Alternaria tomatophila*), *Botrytis cinerea*, *Cladosporium fulvum*, *Colletotrichum coccodes*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Fusarium clavum*, *Leveillula taurica*, *Oidium lycopersici*, *Pseudoidium neolycopersici*, *Pyrenochaeta lycopersici*, *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Septoria lycopersici*, *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum*, *Sclerotium rolfsii*, *Stemphylium* spp., and *Verticillium dahlia* (13).

Several *Alternaria* species are commonly detected on tomatoes, among which the most important are *Alternaria solani*, *Alternaria alternata*, and *Alternaria arborescens*. *Alternaria* toxins in both fresh market and processed tomato products are mainly the result of fungal diseases caused by these three species .

A. solani and *A. alternata* cause a disease named "Early blight". Early blight is present in all tomato growing regions and causes damage wherever a humid climate or frequent dews create conditions for infection. The fungus spends the winter on infected bio-waste in or on the soil, where it can live for at least a year, if not more. It can also be transmitted through seed. The following season, new spores are formed. Water, wind, insects, other animals, including humans, and machinery, all deliver spores. They become the most important source of new spore generation and are responsible for rapid disease transmission once the initial infections have occurred. Conidia are wind disseminated and generally infect during rainy or humid weather when temperatures are between 24-29 °C. Lesions may develop two days after infection under favorable conditions. Plants infected with early blight develop small black or brown spots, usually about 6 to 12 mm in diameter, on leaves, stems, and fruit. Leaf spots are leathery and often have a concentric ring pattern. They usually appear on older leaves first. Spots on fruit are sunken, dry, and may also have a concentric pattern; frequently they occur near the calyx end of the fruit. Infection is more severe on plants stressed by poor fertility or other problems. Infection is heaviest on lower leaves first and defoliation moves from the bottom of the plant up. Lesions appear in the largest numbers when plants are bearing fruit (14).

"Collar rot" of tomato is another disease caused by *A. solani*. Collar rot is mainly a seedbed disease carried to the field on tomato transplants and has been associated with the production of tomato seedlings in open fields. Seedlings

shipped for transplanting develop characteristic dark, sunken stem lesions close to the soil line. As the disease progresses, the lesions girdle the stems, forming collars. Many diseased transplants break at the point of infection, resulting in poor stands, and those that survive generally have impaired growth and fruit production (15).

A. alternata causes also a disease known as "Black mold". Black mold is a disease that occurs in the field after rain or dew on mature tomato fruit. Increased late-season rain raises disease incidence; it is particularly common in late-season processing tomatoes. To germinate, fungal spores require 3 to 5 hours of moisture. They can immediately infect fruit after germination by penetrating the epidermis. Following a period of rain and high humidity, a crop might be severely damaged in 4 to 5 days. Any wounds on the fruit, especially sun-burnt areas, are quickly colonized by the fungus. Brown to black lesions appear on the epidermal tissue of ripe fruit. In warm, humid weather, the fungus sporulates to form a black, velvet-like layer on the surface of the existing lesions. Delays in harvest increase the chance of exposure to rain or dew and the incidence of black mold (16).

A. alternate lycopersici is the causal agent of "Stem canker" in tomato. Free water is necessary for spore germination and infection. Disease spread is favored by rain and dew. Symptoms develop 7 to 10 days after inoculation and develop most rapidly at temperatures around 25°C. Dark brown sunken lesions with characteristic concentric rings develop on green fruit either on plants or during postharvest transit of ripening fruit. The fungus survives on infected tomato debris. Infection occurs when airborne spores land on tomato plants or when plants come in contact with infested soil. It can occur in fields planted with infested transplants (16).

ALTERNARIA DISEASES MANAGEMENT

Crop management is the key to controlling *Alternaria* diseases in tomatoes, and therefore reducing the risk of a higher level of *Alternaria* toxins in the final processed tomato product.

Alternaria diseases can be controlled by three measures: cultural practices, fungicide treatment and the use of resistant varieties. Cultural practices and fungicidal treatment are common practices.

- Eradication of weeds and volunteer solanaceous crop plants.
- Control of volunteers and susceptible weeds.
- Removal and destruction of crop residue at the end of the season. Where this is not practical, plowing residue into the soil to promote breakdown by soil microorganisms and

to physically remove the spore source from the soil surface.

- Promotion of good air circulation by proper spacing of plants.
- Using drip irrigation.
- Orient rows in the direction of prevailing winds, avoid shaded areas and avoid wind barriers.
- Healthy plants with adequate nutrition are less susceptible to the disease.
- Using resistant or tolerant varieties.
- Using fungicides preventatively.

These preventive measures are already in place in our fields, as part of the Codes of Good Agricultural Practices. However, cultural practice alone is not sufficient for the control of *Alternaria*. Each crop and the associated weather conditions can be radically different in a given season and can enhance the emergence of the disease if preventive measures are neglected or disease occurs from an infection in the seedling nursery. As stated earlier, *Alternaria* fungi are not

very demanding in temperature and only need some relative humidity, with rainfall of 5 mm or intense dew with an atmospheric temperature of 18 to 29°C, causing *Alternaria* spp. to be a tomato disease agent that every year, although occasionally, finds conditions to develop. Some models showed that in southern Europe the temperature changes (18.2–38.2°C) associated to climate change may minimize growth of *Alternaria* and mycotoxins contamination because at the higher temperatures most species of this genus cannot grow or produce mycotoxins (2).

Several fungicides have been developed to suppress *Alternaria*, although fungicide treatment is not always economically or environmentally sustainable. Fungicides frequently fail to be effective in the face of severe disease pressure, and regular use of fungicides results in the emergence of new fungicide-resistant isolates as a result of high selection pressure.

TABLE 3 presents currently recommended pesticides for the control of *Alternaria* diseases in tomato.

TABLE 3— Formulations for control of *Alternaria* fungi

Azoxystrobin (a)	Famozadone + Cymoxanil
Azoxystrobin + Difeconazole (a)	Fenamidone (b)
Azoxystrobin + Benzovindiflupyr	Fludioxonil + Fluopyram
Azoxystrobin + Chlorothalonil (b)	Fludioxonil + Pydiflumetofen
Azoxystrobin + Flutriafol (b)	Fluopyram
Bacillus amyloliquefaciens (a) #	Fluopyram + Pyrimethanil
Bacillus subtilis (a) #	Fluoxastrobin
Boscalyd	Flutriafol (b)
Boscalid + Pyraclostrobin (a)	Fluopyram + Trifloxystrobin
Captan (a)	Folpet (a)
Cyprodinil + Difeconazole	Iprodione (b)
Chlorothalonil (b)	Isopyrazam (a)
Chlorothalonil (b) + Cymoxanil	Mancozeb (b)
Chlorothalonil (b) + Oxathiapropilipin	Mancozeb (b) + Zoxamide
Chlorothalonil (b) + Zoxamide	Mandipropamid + Difeconazole (a)
Copper (Oxychloride form) (a)	Metconazole
Copper (As Oxychloride) + Fosetyl (as Aluminium salt) +	Orange oil (a)
Cyflufenamid + Difeconazole (a)	Penthiopyrad
Cymoxanil	Polyoxin (Zinc Salt) (b)
Cymoxanil + Copper (Hydroxide) (a)	Pyraclostrobin + Boscalid
Cymoxanil + Famoxadone	Pyraclostrobin + Fluxapyroxad
Difeconazole	Pyrimethanil
Difeconazole + Fluxapyroxad (a)	Tebuconazole
Dimethomorph + Pyraclostrobin (a)	Tetraconazole
Difeconazole + Cyprodinil	Trifloxystrobin
Difeconazol + Mandipropamid	Zoxamide

(a) Approved for use in Portugal (SIFITO / Tomato)

(b) Not approved under Reg. (EC) No 1107/2009

Acceptable for use on organically grown produce

One of the main risks to human health and sustainable food production is cross-resistance, a phenomenon in which a pathogen that resists one antimicrobial drug simultaneously resists one or more additional compounds. It is most common among antibacterial agents with similar modes of action.

Fungicides with a different modes of action are suitable to alternate in a resistance management program. In California, for example, fungicides are classified according to their mechanism of action. Before rotating to a fungicide with a different mode of action group number, no more than one application of fungicides with mode of action group numbers 1, 4, 9, 11, or 17 should be made; for fungicides with other group numbers, no more than two consecutive applications should be made before rotating to a fungicide with a different mode of action group number (17). Nevertheless, the detection of cross-resistance among different classes of fungicides suggests that the mode of action alone may not be an adequate sole criterion to determine what components to use in the mixture and/or rotation of fungicides in agricultural and medical sects. For instance, the observation of a positive association between the aggressiveness and tolerance of *Alternaria* to mancozeb suggests that intensive application of site non-specific fungicides might simultaneously lead to increased fungicide resistance and enhanced ability to cause diseases in pathogen populations, thereby posing a greater threat to agricultural production. In this case, the use of evolutionary principles in closely monitoring populations and the use of appropriate fungicide applications are important for effective use of the fungicides and durable infectious disease management (18).

A forecaster for *A. solani* on tomato was developed in 1978 to detect periods when environmental conditions are suitable for early blight development and give an effective fungicide application plan (19). The timing of the initial spray treatment for tomato early blight management is critical in order to reduce the number of sprays necessary to manage the disease. Spraying only when environmental conditions in the field are suitable for disease spread is the key to successful and efficient management.

The Rain model (TABLE 4) as well as a similar one named Dew model, that assigns a disease severity value (S) ranging from 0-4 based on the mean daily temperature and the hours of leaf wetness during that day, were originally validated in Pennsylvania, USA. The model has since been adapted for use in timing tomato Black mold sprays in Canada and California, and has also been applied to other crops and diseases (20).

TABLE 4— Early blight of tomato. Disease severity as function of environmental conditions

Temp. average (°C) ^a	Hours RH > 90% ^b	Total rain ^c	R ^d
< 22	< 60	< 2.5	0
> 22	< 60	< 2.5	0
< 22	> 60	< 2.5	1
< 22	< 60	> 2.5	1
< 22	> 60	> 2.5	1
> 22	> 60	< 2.5	2
> 22	> 60	> 2.5	2
> 22	> 60	> 2.5	3

^a Average temperature for past 5 days (°C).

^b Hours of Relative Humidity > 90% during past 5 days.

^c Total rainfall for past 7 days (cm).

^d Disease severity scale: 0 indicates environmental conditions unfavorable for *A. solani* spore formation and infection of tomato; 3 indicates that conditions are highly favorable.

MINIMIZING THE OCCURRENCE OF *ALTERNARIA* TOXINS IN PROCESSED TOMATO PRODUCTS

Reducing the levels of *Alternaria* toxins is now of paramount importance for the industry. One key strategy is, as expected, tomato selection, starting in the field. Diseased tomatoes should not be delivered to the processing plant, and should not be accepted for processing.

Commission Regulation (EC) No 217/2002 of 5 February 2002 fixing eligibility criteria for raw materials under the production aid scheme in Regulation (EC) No 2201/96 is still in use today and establishes that upon reception of each tomato consignment, processors shall examine the quality of the raw material on the basis of samples. The examination shall establish the percentage by weight of defective raw material for each type of defect defined and the total of these percentages, rounded up or down to the nearest whole number. If this total exceeds the 10 % limit, the consignment shall not be eligible for aid. But the Member States may authorize the contracting parties to increase this limit to a maximum of 15 % (21). The referred defects are defined as:

- Foreign matter: foreign matter is considered to be anything other than the fruit itself.
- Diseased, rotten or wormy fruit: fruit attacked by disease, insects or a rotting agent over an area more than 30 mm in diameter, extending into the fruit.

- Green tomatoes: healthy fruit which have not reached maturity and are completely green on the outside.

As said, the total of percentages should not exceed 10 % (or 15 %). In the current situation, it seems obvious that accepting close to 10% of diseased tomatoes (assuming the remaining defects were not significant) cannot be considered a good practice. The processors should fix specific limits for each of the defects, as this is allowed by the Regulation, and consignments exceeding a specific limit—specifically in “diseased tomatoes”— should be rejected. The highest levels of *Alternaria* toxins were found in samples visibly infected with alternariosis, that is, in products obviously not suitable for human consumption. Therefore, if it is not suitable to be consumed in fresh, it should not be considered to be suitable for consumption in processed products, such as tomato paste. Failing to assume this absolute criterion may imply that one single consignment of diseased raw tomato will increase the juice's initial contamination, due to the mixing of several loads prior to processing.

Thermal treatments in the production of processed tomato products, namely sterilization, are not able to inactivate mycotoxins. Most mycotoxins are heat-resistant within the range of tomato-processing temperatures (80–121°C), hence such time-temperature profiles will result in little to no reduction in overall toxin levels (22).

Current development of analytical methods for the determination of *Alternaria* toxins in food commodities shows that such methods are yet technically demanding and time-consuming, therefore not easily included by processors in their monitoring plans (22). An enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) for **TeA** with an LOD of 30 µg/kg, although much less sensitive than the common methods, may be useful as a screening method (23).

CONCLUSIONS

Mycotoxins in general and specifically *Alternaria* toxins, can only be minimized in the final processed tomato products, such as tomato paste, by disease prevention, starting in the field and ending in strict rules set at the point-of-entry in the processor's facilities. No technological processes exist that may inactivate or reduce the mycotoxins in the processing of such products, and certainly, that is not attainable by the heat treatments commonly used in the industry. From a farm-to-factory perspective, these are the author's selected major measures:

- Preference must be given to disease-resistant (including *Alternaria* diseases) tomato varieties.
- Ensure that tomato seedlings, grown in a plant nursery and transplanted to the field, are disease-free.
- Volunteer host plants and solanaceous weeds like *Solanum nigrum*, must be removed from the field.
- Tomato plants should not be raised in known infested fields, or with crop residues from the previous season.
- Flood irrigation must be avoided, drip irrigation is preferred.
- The crop should be monitored for incipient occurrence of diseased plants in the field. Action must be taken as soon as it is observed a single diseased plant.
- Infected plants must be uprooted and buried (at least 50 cm deep) outside the field.
- Field must be drained as quickly as possible after rain. Irrigation frequency must be reduced.
- Weather conditions should be monitored and registered, to evaluate the occurrence of environmental circumstances in the field that are suitable for diseases.
- The disease may be difficult to control due to production practices that result in dense plantings. In such cases, early detection and/or preventative fungicides can help.
- The continuous and extensive use of fungicides with the same mechanism of action results in strong selection for resistant mutants, increasing the development of fungicide resistance. Combining or rotating fungicides with different modes of action results in disruptive selection, which lowers the possibility of the evolution of fungi.
- Organically produced tomato crops—having a reduced set of fungicides available— should be planned so that growing during periods of extended suitable environmental conditions for fungal diseases is minimized. Early blight, for example, can appear rapidly in the middle to late season and is more severe when plants are stressed by insufficient nutrition, dryness, or other diseases.
- Diseased tomatoes should not be accepted at the processing unit. The “diseased, rotten or wormy fruit” defect maximum level should be significantly lower than those accepted for the “foreign matter” and “green tomatoes” defects.
- Processors may have to implement “on-site” laboratorial monitoring programs and cooperate with scientific research institutes for the development of rapid detection kits for *Alternaria* toxins in tomato products.

REFERENCES

1. Moretti A, Pascale M, Logrieco AF. Mycotoxin risks under a climate change scenario in Europe. *Trends Food Sci Technol*. 2019 Feb 1;84:38–40.
2. Perrone G, Ferrara M, Medina A, Pascale M, Magan N. Toxigenic Fungi and Mycotoxins in a Climate Change Scenario: Ecology, Genomics, Distribution, Prediction and Prevention of the Risk. *Microorganisms* [Internet]. 2020 Oct 1 [cited 2022 Apr 5];8(10):1–20.
3. Escrivá L, Oueslati S, Font G, Manyes L. *Alternaria* Mycotoxins in Food and Feed: An Overview. *J Food Qual*. 2017;2017.
4. Crudo F, Varga E, Aichinger G, Galaverna G, Marko D, Dall'Asta C, et al. Co-Occurrence and Combinatory Effects of *Alternaria* Mycotoxins and Other Xenobiotics of Food Origin: Current Scenario and Future Perspectives. *Toxins* 2019, Vol 11, Page 640. 2019 Nov 3;11(11):640.
5. Lehmann L, Wagner J, Metzler M. Estrogenic and clastogenic potential of the mycotoxin alternariol in cultured mammalian cells. *Food Chem Toxicol*. 2006 Mar;44(3):398–408.
6. EFSA. Scientific Opinion on the risks for animal and public health related to the presence of *Alternaria* toxins in feed and food. *EFSA J*. 2011 Oct 1;9(10).
7. Arcella D, Eskola M, Gomez Ruiz JA. Dietary exposure assessment to *Alternaria* toxins in the European population. *EFSA J*. 2016 Dec 1;14(12).
8. EFSA. Call for data on *Alternaria* toxins in food and feed | EFSA [Internet]. 2016 [cited 2022 Apr 5].
9. Varga E, Marko D. Mycotoxins in fruits: *Alternaria* toxins in tomato products. *Fruit Juice Focus* [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2022 Apr 8];(29):22–4.
10. EFSA. COMMISSION RECOMMENDATION of XXX on the monitoring of the presence of *Alternaria* toxins in food [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2022 Apr 5]. Available from: www.efsa.europa.eu/efsajournal
11. European Commission. Commission Recommendation (EU) 2022/553 of 5 April 2022 on monitoring the presence of *Alternaria* toxins in food. *Off J Eur Union* [Internet]. 2022
12. Maximum Residue Limits | CODEX ALIMENTARIUS FAO-WHO [Internet]. [cited 2022 Apr 8]. Available from: <https://www.fao.org/fao-who-codexalimentarius/codex-texts/maximum-residue-limits/en/>
13. Panno S, Davino S, Caruso AG, Bertacca S, Crnogorac A, Mandić A, et al. A review of the most common and economically important diseases that undermine the cultivation of tomato crop in the mediterranean basin. *Agronomy* [Internet]. 2021
14. Early Blight / Tomato / Agriculture: Pest Management Guidelines / UC Statewide IPM Program (UC IPM) [Internet]. [cited 2022 Apr 6].
15. Maiero M, Ng TJ, Barksdale TH. Inheritance of collar rot resistance in the tomato breeding lines C 1943 and NC EBR-2. *Phytopathology*. 1990;80(12):1365–8.
16. Black Mold / Tomato / Agriculture: Pest Management Guidelines / UC Statewide IPM Program (UC IPM) [Internet]. [cited 2022 Apr 6].
17. FRAC | By FRAC Mode of Action Group [Internet]. [cited 2022 Apr 8]. Available from: <https://www.frac.info/fungicide-resistance-management/by-frac-mode-of-action-group>
18. Yang LN, He MH, Ouyang HB, Zhu W, Pan ZC, Sui QJ, et al. Cross-resistance of the pathogenic fungus *Alternaria alternata* to fungicides with different modes of action. *BMC Microbiol* [Internet]. 2019
19. Madden L. FAST, a Forecast System for *Alternaria solani* on Tomato. *Phytopathology*. 1978;68(9):1354.
20. Models: Blackmold of Processing Tomato--UC IPM [Internet]. [cited 2022 Apr 9]. Available from: <http://ipm.ucanr.edu/DISEASE/DATABASE/tomatoblackmold.html>
21. European Commission E. Commission Regulation (EC) No 217/2002 of 5 February 2002 fixing eligibility criteria for raw materials under the production aid scheme in Regulation (EC) No 2201/96. *Eur Union Off J* [Internet]. 2002;L(35):11–2.
22. Simões C. *Bacillus coagulans* as target microorganism in the sterilization of double and triple-concentrated tomato paste. 2022 Apr 4 [cited 2022 Apr 9]; Available from: <https://zenodo.org/record/6411984>
23. Gross M, Asam S, Rychlik M. Evaluation of an enzyme immunoassay for the detection of the mycotoxin tenuazonic acid in sorghum grains and sorghum-based infant food. *Mycotoxin Res* [Internet]. 2017 Feb 1 [cited 2022 Apr 9];33(1):75–8.